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Privacy in Online Social Networking Sites

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Abstract: There are more than 192 active social networking websites. Bringing every kind of social group together in one place and letting them interact is really a big thing indeed .Huge amount of information process in the sites each day, end up making it vulnerable to attack. There is no systematic framework taking into account the importance of privacy. Increased privacy settings don't always guarantee privacy when there is a loop hole in the applications. Lack of user education results is over sharing. Privacy settings to limit access to some data are available, but these settings are never the default. Only a tiny minority make use of these. Online social network does not provide any demarcation line between private and public information. The personal information shared in online social networks can harm the user in often unexpected ways. Private data is available in plenty. The major privacy problems are due to complicated privacy model, implementation errors and economic pressure. Until recently, not much work was done in this area. The recent papers, which I have collected is a Testimony to state that lot of work needs to be done in this area.

Keywords : Social Networking Sites, Online Privacy, Facebook

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past few years online social networks have become highly popular. As of February 2010, Facebook had more than 400 million active users. Every day 50% of those active users logged on to Facebook. In most online social networks users create profiles which often contain details about their personal lives. These profiles are shared with friends, networks and sometimes also with strangers. Some online social networks also provide a platform to share multimedia content like photos and videos. Facebook for instance is one of the largest Photo Sharing Sites worldwide. Every month 3 billion photos are being uploaded to Facebook. **Utilize the "Privacy" settings on your Facebook account—you can adjust your privacy settings so as to control who has access to your personal information.** It's pretty awesome to be able to keep up with people with just a click of a mouse. Yes these days' social networking sites are very useful for online business. You can promote your website, blog or business through Social Networking sites very well.

2. RELATED WORKS

Maximilien, E.M et al., [1], Liu, K., Terzi, E [2], Renner, C [3] focuses on privacy as a fundamental building block for social networks. Bonneau et al.[4] described how online social networks promote their privacy policies and settings with a model in which the provider needs to satisfy the privacy aware users by offering sufficient controls for privacy .

Kelly et. al. [5] take another approach by introducing a "nutrition Label" for privacy. Similar to the nutrition facts label this privacy label shows the user how an internet site treats the user's data. In contrast

to the privacy policies used today such as Platform for Privacy Preferences project [6] such a label could be more easily understood by uneducated users. Dong Hee Shin [7] proposed a study that examines security, trust and privacy concerns with regard to social networking websites among consumer[1-3] focuses on privacy as a fundamental building block for social networks.

3. PROPOSED WORK

From the above discussion, it is evident that privacy issues in online social n/w needs a systematic study. Our proposal would look at the current state of privacy controls in various online social networks and design a new framework for controlling the personal privacy risk.

We would look into the following challenges pertaining to privacy-identification mapping, portability of data, cascaded authorization and build a common enhanced privacy policy framework.

4. RISKS INVOLVED

Today countless number of people involved in social networking site but they don't have awareness what information is public and what information is private. Even though several social networking sites offer data sharing controls, there's no standard framework to say which personal information is shared with whom.

For kids of this generation, who have used Internet-based technologies for many social purposes, posting a profile of one's self and sending messages and files to friends is a natural progression. There are certainly safety concerns that parents and children should discuss -- related to the posting of inappropriate content, personal information, and contact with friends they make online.

Use privacy settings to restrict who can access and post on your child's website. Some social networking sites have settings to limit the information you share with others. Show your child how to use these settings to limit who can view their online profile, and explain to them why this is important. Below are few samples of how to change the preferences in some social networking sites.

While researching social networking behavior, I focused on teen behavior over the past two to three years. In many cases, they have yet to achieve a level of awareness of the consequences associated with their actions.

According to a 2006 survey conducted by the Pew Internet and American Life Project, "more than half of all online American youths, ages 12-17 use online social networking sites."

5. OPEN RESEARCH CHALLENGES

1. Identity Mapping

Users often have multiple identities scattered across various social-networking and third-party sites. For new users of third-party sites, Social Network Connect Services eliminate the need for a tedious registration process.

They also enable users to link an existing account on a third-party site to one on a social-networking site, thereby providing a seamless Social Web experience. For example, Facebook compares the hash values of a user's e-mail address at Facebook with that at a third-party site and, if they match, links them together.

It also uses this approach to connect a user's Facebook friends with third-party site friends. However, this won't work if a user's e-mail address on Face book differs from that on the third-party site. Moreover, if the user's friends have different e-mail addresses, linking their accounts is almost impossible.

Mapping friends' accounts is especially important in protecting user privacy on the Social Web. Unfortunately, current identity-mapping methods like that used by Face book have many shortcomings.

2. User Data Portability

Social Web users often maintain multiple profiles and social graphs on different social-networking sites. For example, a user may have a Face book account to keep in touch with family and friends and a LinkedIn account for professional contacts. Managing these disparate profiles and social graphs is an odd job.

3. Cascaded Authorization

Third-party sites frequently rely on other third-party sites to provide services, which require the sharing of user data from one third-party site to another.

Under current authentication and authorization approaches, users must consent each time a third-party site accesses their data. This approach is both cumbersome and time-consuming.

What's needed is a new authorization mechanism that would obtain a user's consent once for a specific content object and cascade it to all third-party sites.

6. MAJOR ROLE OF SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES:

Once you understand the advantages and disadvantages of social networking, then you can cruise through without fail. Everything about it lies on the advantages and disadvantages of social networking, and what it can do for you.

Way to find a job - Nowadays the big companies have specialists on human resources that search for profiles in these kind of sites to recruit new collaborators. If you're looking for job you can create a profile (a serious, professional and complete profile) and you might be discovered and recruited by a company. You can describe your capabilities and publish some of your works - and with a little luck you can find a job.

Interaction with new people - social networking sites are the perfect spot to meet new people online. With the help of advanced search tools you can find users who have the same interests you do and that can be the starting point of a great friendship and/or relationship. Many people meet online and then stabilize a relationship in real life - getting married, having children, etc. Using both reliable scales and measures.

You can promote your site or business for free - If you have a business or site you need to promote you can do it by creating a business profile on some of these networks. You can load images, your logo, etc. into your profile and it will be visible for your virtual friends and all the users who visit your profile. You can also put topics on groups related to your business and stabilize new contacts that can lead to sales, subscriptions or anything else.

7. CONCLUSION

The range of privacy settings that OSNs provide were found to be permissive since default settings allow access to strangers in all OSNs. Online social networking offers people great convenience for social networking. It allows people to keep in touch with friends, reconnect with old friends or acquaintances, meet new people, and even conduct business with the click of a few buttons. You can find people with similar interests as you and get to know them better, even if they are in a different country without having to worry about an enormous phone bill or going over

the restricted minutes on a phone card. However, like all things, nothing can be too good to be true. Mapping friends account is especially important in protecting user privacy on social web. One ideal solution is that all users have global unique identity offered by an opened service provider. Social Web users often maintain multiple profiles and social graphs on different social-networking sites. Managing these disparate profiles and social graphs can be a big problem. One possible solution is for users to maintain a global profile and social graph in one place. They could then create sub profiles.

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